

The Special Relativistic $\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ Factor and the Notion of Length in (0,ct) Part II

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In Part I, we considered a Lorentz transformation of two 4-vectors, $(x=0, ct)$ and $(x=L, t=0)$. These transform to: (gvt, gt) and $(gL, gLv/c)$ respectively, where $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Here we try to ask why a vector $(L,0)$ with $t=0$ in the rest frame should have a time $= v/c gL$ in the moving? We argue that there are two considerations in the moving frame. First, there is a position in space of a point $(x=L)$ in the rest frame which has nothing to do with motion, but then because the particle is seen to be moving, its overall position - translated rest position = v time elapsed in the moving frame because $(0,0) \rightarrow (0,0)$. In particular, gL is the overall position and $v gLv/c$, the time multiplied by v , so the translated rest position = $L \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, i.e. the Lorentz contraction.

In the case of $(x=0, ct)$, there is no translated rest position, so overall position = v time elapsed, where values of overall position and time elapsed hold in the moving frame. We also show that by these arguments, $(L,0) \rightarrow (gL, gLv/c)$ cannot have $g=1$ which one might be tempted to use from $(x=0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt)$. In other words, a $g(v)$ factor must exist and serve to modify x and t values in the moving frame. $(g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc})$.

Rest and Moving Frames

Special relativity may be formulated in terms of measurements of the same object in rest and moving frames. In the rest frame, x and t are decoupled. Nevertheless, the concept of a length holds in a rest frame and one may measure each end point $x=0$ and $x=L$ at the same time $t=0$ (or at different times if one wishes).

In the moving frame, one must sense motion at a constant speed v if the frame moves at a constant $-v$. At the same time, one must sense some original length from the rest frame. Thus:

The position in the moving frame = the "sense of the original length in the rest frame" + $v t'$,
((1))

where t' is the time elapsed in the moving frame because $(x=0, t=0)$ maps to $(0,0)$. We apply ((1)) to the two cases of $(x=0, t)$ and $(x=L, t=0)$ in the rest frame.

The Lorentz transformation for these two vectors is:

$(x=0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt)$ where $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((2a)) and

$(x=L, t=0) \rightarrow (gL, gLv/c)$ ((2b))

We consider the scenario of ((2b)) first. In this case, there is a length in the rest frame of L even though $t=0$. T is completely decoupled from L . Now, one might consider $x=L$ to be a point, but the four vector $(0,0)$ which maps to $(0,0)$ shows that one may think in terms of intervals.

Thus, in the moving frame, one must see a “sense of original length”, where the original length is L . At the same, the entire interval (which was $(0,L)$ in the rest frame) is moving and if one has t' , then the interval is $t'-0$ (from $(0,0)$) so the object should have moved an extra distance of vt' in the moving frame. Using ((1)) means that:

$$gL = \text{overall position in moving frame} = \text{“sense of original length”} - v (gLv/c) \quad ((3))$$

Here $t'=gLv/c$.

This leads to: sense of original length = $L \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((4)), but this is the Lorentz contraction. In other words, an L in a rest frame is seen to be $L \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in the moving frame, but if $x'-0$ is not this length, then there must have been some motion at speed v for the time $t'-0$.

Implications

We consider the case of $(L,0) \rightarrow (gL, gLv/c)$. One may see that if $v=c$, then one has (gL, gL) , i.e. the length and time intervals are the same as one has from $x=ct$ with $c=1$. If $v=0$, then one is back at the rest mass scenario. In other words, the sense of original length dominates because the velocity is so low that gL is essentially L .

Now in Part I, we argued that if one only considers the transformation $(x=0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt)$, then one might be tempted to set $g=1$. The transformation $(L,0) \rightarrow (gL, gLv/c)$ would mean that setting $g=1$, one has L and $t=Lv/c$. The problem with this is that one has the same L from the rest frame, but given that there is elapsed time (from $(0,0) \rightarrow (0,0)$), the object should be at a greater distance than L due to the travel of $v Lv/c$. This means that g cannot be 1 and one must consider a modification factor of g which turns out to be $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Thus, a modification factor $g(v)$ must appear in the moving frame.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even if one considers 4-vector point transformations via a Lorentz matrix, e.g. $(x=0, t)$ ($c=1$), given that $(0,0) \rightarrow (0,0)$ means that one may think of intervals. We argue that if one has a length in the rest frame $x=0, x=L$, then there must be a sense of this length in the moving frame in addition to the sense of overall motion which could move the x =modified L point to a greater distance because $v (t'-0)$ is this extra distance where t' is the travel time. Thus:

$$X' = \text{sense of original length} - v t' \quad ((A))$$

We apply this to both $(x=0, t)$ and $(x=L,0)$ in the rest frame. In the first case, there is no original length because $(0,0)$ and $(0,t)$ are both at $x=0$. Thus, any x' position is solely due to motion vt' . One might at this point think that $t'=t$ instead of $t' = g(v) t$. If, however, one considers $(x=L,0)$, then this Lorentz transforms to $(gL, gL v/c)$. If one were to set $g=1$, one would have the original length L in the moving frame which means that no motion has occurred and t' should be 0, but

instead it would be Lv/c (for $g=1$). Thus, g cannot be one and there must be a modification factor of $g(v)$ for times and lengths seen in the moving frame. We note that the sense of the original length L in the moving frame is $L \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, the Lorentz contracted length.